

A Review of Existing Blended Learning Models in Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

This review study looks at the several blended learning models that are being used in higher education today and offers a thorough examination of their features, methods of implementation, and effects on the learning outcomes of students. Blended learning has come a long way, providing students with more flexibility, customization, and engagement through the combination of online and in-person teaching approaches. Key paradigms such as Flex, Enriched Virtual, A La Carte, and Rotation (Station Rotation, Lab Rotation, Flipped Classroom) are categorized and examined in this article. Every model is examined with respect to its distinct attributes, approaches for implementation, and advantages and disadvantages. Best practices for successfully incorporating these models into higher education are also covered in the article, with a focus on the significance of precise learning objectives, teacher preparation, student assistance, flexible scheduling, and reliable evaluation techniques. This study intends to assist educators and policymakers in optimizing blended learning settings to improve student learning outcomes in higher education by offering a complete evaluation of current blended learning models.

Keywords: Blended Learning Models, Flipped Classroom Model, Flex Model, Rotation Model, Enriched Virtual Model, A La Carte Model,

Introduction

In 2003, the Australian National Training Authority (ANTA) defined blended learning as the integration of traditional learning with web-based online methodologies. "Blended learning focuses on the achievement of learning objectives by applying the right personal learning technologies to watch the right personal learning style to transfer the right skills to the right person at the right time" (Singh, 2003). "Blended learning has also been conceptualised in terms of combining traditional in-class learning with online activities and resources" (Downes, (2008)).

"Blended learning should be viewed as a pedagogical approach that combines the effectiveness and socialization opportunities of the classroom with the technologically enhanced active learning possibilities of the online environment, rather than a ratio of delivery modalities" (Ferdig, Cavanaugh, DiPietro, and Black, 2009).

Blended learning, which combines online digital material with traditional face-to-face classroom approaches, has grown rapidly in higher education. This pedagogical method seeks to blend the benefits of traditional and online learning environments in order to improve the overall educational experience (Graham, 2013). The

increased availability of digital tools and resources has enabled educators to design more flexible and personalized learning experiences that address a wide range of student needs (Means et al., 2014).

The notion of blended learning is not new, but its popularity has grown in recent years due to technological improvements and the demand for more adaptable educational approaches. Given the emergence of digital technologies and the emerging importance of leveraging technology for teaching-learning at all levels from school to higher education, the NEP 2020 recommends for use of blended models of learning (6100340_Concept-Note-Blended-Mode-of-Teaching-and-Learning.Pdf, n.d.). As higher education institutions work to meet the needs of a diverse and global student population, blended learning has emerged as a viable solution with numerous advantages, including improved access to education, increased student engagement, and the potential for more effective learning outcomes (Dziuban, Hartman, & Moskal, 2004).

Several blended learning methods have been created and deployed at various higher education institutions. These models differ in terms of structure, implementation tactics, and the degree to which they combine online and face-to-face components. The flipped classroom, enriched virtual model, and rotation model are three of the most widely discussed models, each with its own set of features and benefits (Horn & Staker, 2014). Understanding these models and their efficacy is critical for educators and policymakers making educated decisions about the implementation and design of blended learning programs.

This article will examine the present blended learning models in higher education, including their essential characteristics, implementation methodologies, and impact on student learning outcomes. By assessing each model's strengths and drawbacks, this review aims to provide insights into best practices and recommendations for future blended learning research and implementation.

Existing blended learning strategies in higher education are diverse and address a variety of educational goals and circumstances. Here are some of the most widely used models:

1. Flipped Classroom Model
2. Enriched Virtual Model
3. Rotation Model
4. Flex Model
5. A La Carte Model
6. Lab Rotation Model

Flipped Classroom Model

The flipped classroom model is a pedagogical technique that reverses the usual learning environment by offering instructional information outside of the classroom, most often online. During class time, students are engaged in active learning activities such as exercises, projects, and discussions.

Key Characteristics

1. **Pre-Class Instruction:** Students acquire lecture content before class via videos, texts, or podcasts.
2. **Active Learning:** Classroom activities promote higher-order thinking skills like problem-solving, teamwork, and application of knowledge.
3. **Student-Centered Learning:** It focuses on personalized learning, allowing students to progress at their own speed and review content as needed.
4. **Formative Assessment:** Frequent formative exams check student comprehension and provide timely feedback.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Content Delivery:** Using a learning management system (LMS), create and disperse pre-class resources like readings, interactive modules, and video lectures.
2. **In-Class Activities:** Create engaging and cooperative exercises including group discussions, problem-solving exercises, and practical projects for your students.

3. **Evaluation and Feedback:** Use formative evaluations to find out how well students are learning the material and modify your lesson plans accordingly. For ongoing feedback, make use of resources like quizzes, peer reviews, and class discussions.
4. **Technology Integration:** Make use of technology to create material (such as video editing software) and to involve students in the classroom (such as interactive whiteboards and online forums).

Impact on Student Learning Outcomes

- **Better Engagement:** According to Bishop and Verleger (2013), the use of active learning techniques in the classroom raises student participation and engagement.
- **Improved Understanding:** During in-class activities, students have more chances to apply their knowledge and get clarification on any questions they may have, which improves their comprehension and memory of the subject (Karabulut-Ilgu et al., 2018; Naik, 2023).
- **Flexible Learning:** To meet the requirements and styles of a wide range of learners, students can study at their own speed and review pre-class materials as needed (Lage, Platt, & Treglia, 2000).

Advantages

1. **Personalized Learning:** This approach caters to the unique learning needs of each student by allowing them to set their own learning pace and access information at any time.
2. **Increased Interaction:** Interactive and collaborative activities take up less classroom time, encouraging peer participation and deeper learning.
3. **More Productive Use of Classroom Time:** By emphasizing knowledge application over passive listening, classroom time is more effectively utilized.
4. **Greater Student Involvement:** Students become more motivated and involved in active learning activities.

Limitations

1. **Preparation Time:** Creating and selecting pre-class materials takes a lot of time and work from instructors.
2. **Student Accountability:** This approach depends on students finishing their assignments before class on their own, which may not always happen regularly.
3. **Technology Access:** Some learners may find it difficult to obtain consistent access to technology and the internet.
4. **Initial Resistance:** Adapting from traditional teaching methods to a flipped classroom approach may encounter resistance from both students and educators.

Enriched Virtual Model

The enhanced virtual model is a blended learning strategy that includes in-person and online training; but, unlike other models, it does not require students to spend the bulk of their time in the physical classroom. Instead, students may attend in-person interactions on occasion while doing the majority of their schoolwork online.

Key Characteristics

1. **Intermittent Face-to-Face Sessions:** Instead of daily or weekly sessions, students meet with teachers in-person on a regular basis.
2. **Online Learning:** Most instruction and coursework are given online, promoting flexibility and self-paced learning.
3. **Personalized Learning Paths:** Online learning allows students to set their own speed and schedule, leading to a more personalized experience.
4. **Flexible Scheduling:** This strategy is suitable for students with various schedules, such as employment, family, or other responsibilities.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Online Content Delivery:** Create and distribute course materials using an online learning management system (LMS). This might include video lectures, readings, quizzes, and interactive exercises.
2. **Schedule regular in-person sessions:** for talks, assessments, hands-on activities, and individualized assistance. These sessions might be scheduled monthly, biweekly, or at different intervals.
3. **Assistance Systems:** Offer online resources like forums, virtual office hours, and email assistance to assist students with inquiries and challenges.
4. **Assess and Feedback:** Use online quizzes, assignments, and in-person assessments to evaluate student progress and offer prompt feedback.

Impact on Student Learning Outcomes

- **Flexibility and Accessibility:** Allows students to access course materials at their own pace, making education more accessible (Means et al., 2014).
- **Improved Self Discipline:** Fosters self-regulation and time management abilities, essential for lifelong learning (Watson, 2008).
- **Potential for Personalised Learning:** Personalized learning allows students to advance at their own speed, resulting in improved retention and comprehension (Horn & Staker, 2014).

Strengths

1. **High Flexibility:** Adapts to different student schedules and enables studying anytime, anywhere.
2. **Personalized Learning:** Students may customize their learning experiences and proceed at their own speed.
3. **Resource Efficiency:** Reduces the need for physical classroom space, potentially lowering expenses for institutions and students.
4. **Enhanced Access:** Offers options for students who cannot attend regular classes owing to geographical, economical, or personal reasons.

Weaknesses

1. **Limited in-person interaction:** Limited in-person interaction might cause feelings of loneliness and lack of instant support.
2. **Required Self-Discipline:** Success in this approach depends on students' abilities to manage their time and stay motivated without continual monitoring.
3. **Technology Dependence:** Some learners may struggle with accessing technology and the internet on a consistent basis.
4. **Instructor Adaptation:** Instructors need to be skilled and smart enough to create interesting online content and manage both online and in-person components.

Rotation Model

Students that use the rotation model, a blended learning strategy, alternate between several learning modes, including online learning. By utilizing the advantages of each modality, this approach aims to improve the educational experience by offering a well-balanced combination of in-person instruction, group/collaborative tasks, and online learning.

Key Characteristics

1. **Station Rotation:** Based on a predetermined timetable or at the teacher's discretion, students move between several stations. These stations usually consist of online learning, cooperative exercises, small-group teaching, and individual practice.
2. **Flexibility:** The model is adaptable to many disciplines and educational levels, enabling adaptation according to the objectives of the lesson and the needs of the students.

3. **Teacher Facilitation:** Teachers are essential in helping students complete group projects, offering individualized support, and navigating rotations.
4. **Integrated Evaluation:** Every station incorporates continuous evaluation to track student progress and give prompt feedback.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Creating Rotations:** Arrange and set up stations that include in-person instruction, online learning, group tasks, and solitary work. Make sure every station focuses on certain learning goals.
2. **Scheduling:** Create a rotation plan that enables pupils to spend enough time at each station. Depending on the subject and the demands of the instructor, the timetable may be daily or weekly.
3. **Technology Integration:** Make use of digital materials, learning management systems (LMS), and instructional software for the online learning station.
4. **Formative Assessment:** Use formative evaluations at every station to determine how well students are grasping the material and to guide instructional modifications. To collect data, use observation, quizzes, and student reflections.
5. **Teacher Support:** Provide teachers with continuous professional development that focuses on technology use and individualized education so they can manage and support the rotation model successfully.

Impact on Students Learning Outcomes

- **Engagement and Motivation:** Students are kept interested and motivated by the diversity of activities and modalities, which accommodate various learning preferences (Staker & Horn, 2012).
- **Deeper Understanding and Retention of Content:** Personalized education and the chance to review concepts in various formats might enhance comprehension and retention of content (Tucker, 2012; Ayob et al. 2020).
- **Collaboration abilities:** Collaborative stations help students develop their communication and cooperation abilities while preparing them for real-world situations (Christensen et al. 2011).

Advantages

1. **Personalized Learning:** Enables education to be tailored and differentiated according to the requirements and development of each learner.
2. **Rich and Diverse Learning Experiences:** Blends several teaching strategies to provide a comprehensive and varied learning environment.
3. **Enhanced Engagement:** Lessens monotony and keeps children interested with a variety of activities.
4. **Data-Driven Instruction:** Useful information from ongoing assessments is used to improve student results and teaching strategies.

Limitations

1. **Complex preparation:** To guarantee seamless transitions and efficient use of time at each station, meticulous preparation and organization are necessary.
2. **Resource-Intensive:** Requires sufficient resources, which some schools may find difficult to supply, such as technology, space, and supplies.
3. **Teacher Training:** In order to properly manage and support the rotations, instructors must undergo substantial professional development.
4. **Technology Dependence:** The online learning component depends on technology, which may be a challenge for pupils without dependable access.

Flex Model

The Flex model is a blended learning strategy in which teachers primarily train students online and offer help as needed in small group or one-on-one tutoring sessions. This model's adaptability lets students go forward at their own speed while still getting individualized help and assistance from teachers.

Key Characteristics

1. **Online Learning as the Foundation:** The majority of instruction is given online, giving students access to digital tools, information, and tests.
2. **Personalized help:** Instructors adapt their lessons to each student's requirements by providing help in small groups or one-on-one meetings.
3. **Self-Paced Learning:** This type of learning allows for individualized learning pathways as students are free to proceed through the subject at their own speed.
4. **Flexible Scheduling:** The concept is appropriate for a range of learning environments and student demands since it can accommodate different student schedules.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Creating Online Content:** Provide extensive online learning resources that may be accessed via a learning management system (LMS), such as readings, interactive exercises, video lectures, and exams.
2. **Arranging Assistance Meetings:** Schedule frequent one-on-one or small group meetings so that educators may answer concerns from students, foster dialogue, and offer focused assistance.
3. **Tracking Progress:** To track students' advancement and pinpoint areas in which further help is required, use formative evaluations and data analytics.
4. **Offering Training:** Give educators access to professional development so they can efficiently oversee online learning and offer personalized assistance.

Impact on Students Learning Outcomes

- **Increased Flexibility:** Students have more control over their learning process when they may follow their own schedule and learn at their own speed according to the model (Horn & Staker, 2014).
- **Enhanced Engagement:** Students' motivation and engagement may be enhanced by providing them with individualized support and the freedom to go at their own speed (Means et al. 2010).
- **Greater Achievement:** Research indicates that the Flex model can result in better academic achievement, especially for learners who do well in self-paced settings (Tucker, 2012).

Advantages

1. **High Flexibility:** All students may access education more easily since it can accommodate a variety of schedules and learning styles.
2. **Personalized Learning:** Offers chances for tailored guidance and assistance, taking into account the distinctive requirements and speed of every learner.
3. **Efficient Use of Resources:** minimizes the requirement for physical classroom space by making the most use of online resources.
4. **Student Autonomy:** Encourages independence and self-control by giving students the tools they need to take charge of their education.

Limitations

1. **Dependency on Self-Motivation:** May be difficult for certain pupils, but demands a high degree of self-discipline and motivation from them.
2. **Technology Accessibility:** This approach depends on students having consistent access to technology and the internet, which may be a challenge for them.
3. **Teacher Training:** In order to properly oversee and assist with online and customized learning, teachers must complete extensive training.
4. **Limited Face-to-Face engagement:** Less in-person engagement might make some students feel alone and make it more difficult to create a vibrant classroom environment.

A La Carte Model

Under the A La Carte model, which is a blended learning strategy, students can choose to attend certain course/s in a traditional face-to-face format while taking one or more courses fully online. With the flexibility this model affords, students may tailor their educational experiences to suit their interests and requirements.

Key Characteristics

1. **Online Course Options:** While enrolled in certain course/s in a traditional classroom, students have the option to study other courses online.
2. **Customization:** Gives students the freedom to design an education that best suits their schedules, learning preferences, and academic objectives by letting them choose online courses.
3. **Dual Learning settings:** Students utilize the advantages of both in-person and virtual learning settings as they navigate them.
4. **Flexible Pacing:** Self-paced learning is a common feature of online courses, giving students the freedom to advance at their own speed.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Choose a Course:** Provide a selection of online courses that enhance the conventional curriculum. Make certain that these courses adhere to academic standards and are well-designed.
2. **LMS Integration:** To provide online courses, monitor student progress, and help students and instructors communicate, make use of a powerful learning management system (LMS).
3. **Student Support:** Offer academic counseling, technological help, and online resource access to students who are learning online.
4. **Training for Teachers:** Make sure that educators have received training in online teaching techniques and are adept at utilizing the LMS and other technological resources.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Use continuous assessment techniques in both in-person and virtual learning environments to track student development and give prompt feedback.

Impact on Students Learning Outcomes

- **Greater Flexibility:** Students may plan their schedules to accommodate other obligations, which may improve their general satisfaction and retention rates (Means et al. 2014).
- **Enhanced Learning Opportunities:** Students may explore a variety of interests and learn more about a variety of subjects by having access to a wider number of courses, even ones that aren't offered in a traditional environment (Staker & Horn, 2012).
- **Better Self-Management abilities:** By taking online courses, students gain valuable abilities in self-discipline, time management, and independent learning (Watson, 2008).

Strengths

1. **Customization:** Offers students the freedom to tailor their education to suit their own requirements and tastes.
2. **Wider Course Access:** Increases enrollment in advanced or specialized courses that would not be available in a typical classroom.
3. **Flexibility:** Takes into account the varied schedules of students, enabling them to manage their studies alongside other obligations like jobs or extracurricular activities.
4. **Development of Skills:** Encourages the development of self-discipline, time management, and self-directed study skills.

Limitations

1. **Consistency Problems:** It can be difficult to balance in-person and online learning, which could result in variations in student performance and interest.
2. **Technology Access:** May not be available to all students, but requires consistent access to technology and the internet.

3. **Isolation:** Some students may experience feelings of social disengagement and isolation as a result of the decreased in-person interaction found in online courses.
4. **Workload of Teachers:** Teachers may have more work to do and struggle to balance their duties in both regular classroom settings and online learning environments.

Lab Rotation Model

Under the Lab Rotation model, which is a blended learning strategy, students alternate between several learning modalities, including a computer lab where they participate in online learning exercises. This paradigm combines traditional in-person instruction with supervised, regulated online learning.

Key Characteristics

1. **Designated Computer Lab:** Pupils can utilize a specially equipped computer lab that is furnished with tools and materials for virtual education.
2. **Scheduled Rotations:** Students follow a set timetable for switching between computer lab and regular classroom education.
3. **Online Learning Component:** Students participate in online learning exercises in the computer lab, which include digital assignments, interactive modules, and simulations.
4. **Supervised Environment:** The computer lab sessions are supervised by a teacher or facilitator who offers direction, support, and technical help as required.

Implementation Strategies

1. **Lab Setup:** Create a special computer lab equipped with enough tools and technology to facilitate online learning.
2. **Scheduling:** Create a rotating timetable that maintains consistency with regular classroom instruction while enabling students to spend allocated time in the computer lab.
3. **Curriculum Integration:** Align online learning materials and activities with standards and learning objectives by incorporating them into the current curriculum.
4. **Teacher Training:** Give educators the professional development they need to oversee the lab rotation model successfully, including tracking students' progress and incorporating online learning into their lessons.

Impact on Student Learning Outcomes

- **Better Resource Access:** Students' learning experiences are enhanced by the abundance of online tools and resources available to them (Staker & Horn, 2012).
- **Enhanced Engagement:** Students' motivation and engagement levels can be raised by the interactive nature of online learning activities (Means et al. 2010).
- **Personalized Learning:** By customizing online exercises to each student's requirements and preferred method of learning, learning results can be enhanced (Horn & Staker, 2014).

Advantages

1. **Resource Access:** Offers a range of online tools and materials that might not be available in a conventional classroom.
2. **Engagement:** Involves students in technology-enhanced, interactive learning activities to boost their interest and motivation.
3. **Supervised Learning:** Facilitates tailored and supervised learning experiences with teachers offering direction and assistance.
4. **Flexibility:** Allows for scheduling and pacing flexibility to accommodate various learning styles and demands.

Limitations

1. **Technology Dependence:** Some students may find this to be a hurdle because it requires dependable technology and internet connectivity.
2. **Infrastructure Requirements:** May be expensive to establish and maintain; calls for specialized computer labs and resources.
3. **Limited Interactivity:** The depth of engagement and teamwork seen in traditional classroom settings may be absent from online learning activities.
4. **Teacher Training:** To successfully incorporate online learning into their lessons, instructors need a great deal of assistance and training.

There are several methods available for blended learning that integrate online and in-person training; each has advantages and features of its own. Students transition between several learning modes as part of the Rotation models, which include Station Rotation, Lab Rotation, and Flipped Classroom. Students have differing degrees of influence over how their online and in-person learning is blended using the Flex, Self-Blend, and Enriched Virtual models. Students can enroll in specific online courses in addition to regular classroom courses under the A La Carte concept.

The following are some best practices for integrating blended learning:

1. **Well-defined Learning Goals:** Make sure the in-person and virtual components complement one another and are in accordance with the learning objectives.
2. **Teacher Training:** Give educators access to professional development opportunities so they can successfully use technology and internet resources into their instruction.
3. **Student Support:** Provide materials and assistance to students so they can stay interested and navigate online components.
4. **Flexible Scheduling:** Give yourself flexibility in scheduling to meet the requirements and preferences of a wide range of students.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** To track student progress and give timely feedback, use a combination of formative and summative tests.

By putting these best practices into practice, teachers may build blended learning environments that are more productive and improve student learning outcomes.

Acknowledgement: we would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to the Government of Uttar Pradesh for the financial support provided to our project entitled 'Effect of Blended Learning on Academic Achievement and Attitude of Student Teachers at B.Ed. Level' under the Research and Development (R&D) program 2021-22. This review paper is a part of the abovementioned Project.

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